

Kinetic and interfacial studies on transparent organic alloys of succinonitrile-acetanilide system

H. Shekhar and Vishnu Kant*

Department of Chemistry, V. K. S. University, Ara-802 301, Bihar, India

E-mail : invishnukant@gmail.com

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Abstract : The growth mechanism of transparent organic alloys of succinonitrile-acetanilide system has been observed from binary molten mixture by means of measuring the rate of movement of the solid-liquid interface. Parabolic variation in the system with growth velocity (v) at different undercoolings (ΔT), $v = u(\Delta T)^n$ evinces the dislocation growth mechanism. The solid-liquid interface energy (σ) of the alloys has been evaluated from their enthalpies of fusion data. The Gibbs-Thomson coefficient (τ), grain boundary energy (σ_{gb}) and entropy of fusion (ΔS_f) per unit volume have been determined by numerical method. Interface morphology of the alloys follows the Jackson's surface roughness (α) theory for the atomically rough (nonfaceted/metallic) and smooth (faceted/nonmetallic) materials. The thermodynamic mixing functions of the system suggest the nature of molecular interaction in the molecules.

Keywords : Growth kinetics, interfacial energy, mixing function, microstructure.

Introduction

It is well known that succinonitrile (SCN), a material having low entropy of fusion (3.9 kJ mol^{-1}) leads isotropic/nonfaceted/metal like/rough interface¹⁻⁵ growth and acetanilide (ACT), a material having high entropy of fusion (19.6 kJ mol^{-1}) leads anisotropic/faceted nonmetallic growth⁶⁻⁸ with smooth surface. In the present work the nonfaceted-faceted (SCN-ACT) binary system has been undertaken to study the growth kinetics, solid-liquid interfacial energy, Gibbs-Thomson coefficient, grain boundary energy, and microstructure and mixing functions.

Experimental

Materials were purified and the solid-liquid equilibrium data of the system was determined by thaw-melt method⁹. The linear velocity of crystallization of components and alloys (A_1 to A_8 in Table 1) of the binary system was determined by measuring the rate of movement of the growth front in a glass capillary of U-shape. Heat of fusion was determined by DTA method using Stanton Redcroft STA-780 series unit. Microstructures were recorded¹⁰ with help of a camera fitted microscope (Leitz Laborlux D).

Table 1. Heat of fusion (ΔH), crystallization parameter (u and n) and activity coefficient for SCN-ACT system

Alloy SCN-ACT system	Mole fraction of SCN	Melting temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	ΔH (kJ mol^{-1})	u ($\text{mm s}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	n	$\ln \gamma_1$	$\ln \gamma_2$
A_1	0.160	107	17.06	4.57×10^{-4}	3.18	2.014	0.028
A_2	0.295	101	14.78	6.92×10^{-3}	1.60	1.366	0.109
A_3	0.420	97	12.77	2.51×10^{-3}	2.50	1.008	0.233
A_4	0.530	92	10.98	8.71×10^{-3}	2.00	0.761	0.356
A_5	0.630	88	9.38	8.71×10^{-3}	3.70	0.579	0.518
A_6	0.720	82	7.92	2.88×10^{-3}	3.11	0.428	0.712
A_7	0.800	72	6.61	9.50×10^{-3}	2.00	0.290	0.820
A_8	0.870	65	5.40	7.59×10^{-3}	2.67	0.178	1.132
SCN	1.00	54	3.90	2.92×10^{-2}	2.27		
ACT	1.00	116	19.6	5.01×10^{-4}	3.50		

Results and discussion

The Table 1 reports that the composition of alloys A₁, A₂, A₃, A₄, A₅, A₆, A₇ and A₈ of binary system is 0.160, 0.295, 0.420, 0.530, 0.630, 0.720, 0.800 and 0.870 mole fraction of SCN respectively. In order to study the crystallization behavior of binary alloys (A₁ to A₈), the crystallization velocity (v) was determined at different undercoolings (ΔT) and it was found that all the alloys follow dissolution growth mechanism of the Hillig-Turnbull relation¹¹ :

$$v = u(\Delta T)^n \quad (1)$$

where u and n are constant depending on solidification behavior of the phases involved. The value of u and n is evaluated from $\ln v$ versus $\ln \Delta T$ plot. The values of u and n for pure SCN, ACT and alloys are reported in Table 1. The u value for A₁ is lower than that of the parent components. It suggests the phases grow by the alternate nucleation mechanism. On the other hand, all alloys except A₁ having u value not lower than that of pure components evinces the crystallization takes place by the side-by-side growth of two phases. These observations can be explained in the light of the mechanism proposed by Winegard *et al.*¹². According to them the crystallization of binary eutectic alloy begins with the nucleation of one of the component phases having high melting temperature. This would grow until the surrounding liquid becomes rich in the other component. As a result of increased concentration the second component also nucleates. In the SCN-ACT system, ACT nucleate first followed by the nucleation of SCN and in alloys A₂ to A₈ solidification mechanism follows side-by-side nucleation of the component phases.

It is obvious that the effective entropy change and the volume fraction of phases in the alloy are inter-related to decide the interface morphology during solidification and the volume fraction of the two phases depends on the ratio of effective entropy change of the phases. The entropy of fusion value of alloys is calculated by heat of fusion values of the materials. The effective entropy change per unit volume (ΔS_v) is given by :

$$\Delta S_v = \frac{\Delta H}{T} \cdot \frac{1}{V_m} \quad (2)$$

where ΔH is the enthalpy change, T is the melting temperature and V_m is the molar volume of solid phase. The entropy of fusion per unit volume (ΔS_v) for SCN and ACT was found 1.47×10^5 and $4.55 \times 10^5 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-3}$ respectively. Values of ΔS_v for alloys are reported in Table 2.

It has been found that an experimentally observed value of σ keeps a variation of 50–100% from one worker to other. However, Singh and Glickman³ were calculated the solid-liquid interfacial energy (σ) from melting enthalpy change and values obtained are found in good agreement with the experimental values. Turnbull empirical relationship¹³ between the interfacial energy and enthalpy change provides the clue to determine the interfacial energy value of alloy and is expressed as :

$$\sigma = \frac{C\Delta H}{(N)^{1/3}(V_m)^{2/3}} \quad (3)$$

where the coefficient C lies between 0.33 to 0.35 for nonmetallic system, V_m is molar volume and N is the

Table 2. Entropy of fusion per unit volume (S_v), interfacial energy (σ), Gibbs-Thomson coefficient (τ), grain boundary energy (σ_{gb}) and roughness parameter (α)

Alloy	$\Delta S_v \times 10^5$ ($\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-3}$)	$\sigma \times 10^{-3}$ (J m^{-2})	$\sigma_{gb} \times 10^{-3}$ (J m^{-2})	$\tau \times 10^{-8}$ (Km)	α
SCN	1.47	8.2	15.84	5.58	1.43
ACT	0.46	33.2	64.14	72.17	6.07
A ₁	4.20	29.6	57.42	7.03	5.40
A ₂	3.83	26.30	51.02	6.87	4.76
A ₃	3.46	23.17	44.95	6.70	4.15
A ₄	3.11	20.37	39.52	6.55	3.62
A ₅	2.77	17.80	34.58	6.43	3.13
A ₆	2.45	15.30	29.68	6.24	2.69
A ₇	2.17	13.10	25.41	6.04	2.31
A ₈	1.86	10.80	20.95	5.81	5.81

Avogadro's constant. The value of the solid-liquid interfacial energy of succinonitrile and acetanilide was found to be 8.2×10^{-3} and $33.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ J m}^{-2}$ respectively and σ value of alloys was given in Table 2.

The driving force of solidification (ΔG_v) is opposed by the increase in surface free energy due to creation of a new solid-liquid interface. By assuming that solid phase nucleates as small spherical cluster of radius arising due to random motion of atoms within liquid. The critical size or radius (r^*) is related to undercooling (ΔT) and can be expressed by the Chadwick relation¹⁴ :

$$r^* = \frac{2\sigma}{\Delta G_v} = \frac{2\sigma T}{\Delta H_v \Delta T} \quad (4)$$

where σ is the interfacial energy and ΔT and ΔH_v are the melting temperature and the enthalpy of fusion of the compound per unit volume, respectively. The critical size of the nucleus for the components and alloys was calculated at different undercoolings and values are presented in Table 3. It can be inferred from table that the size of the critical nucleus decreases with increase in the undercooling of the melt. The existence of embryo and a range of embryo size can be expected in the liquid in any temperature.

For a planar grain boundary on planar solid-liquid interface the Gibbs-Thomson coefficient (τ) for the system can be calculated by the Gibbs-Thomson equation⁴ is expressed as :

$$\tau = r\Delta T = \frac{TV_m\sigma}{\Delta H} = \frac{\sigma}{\Delta S_v} \quad (5)$$

where τ is the Gibbs-Thomson coefficient, ΔT is the dis-

persion in equilibrium temperature and, r is the radius of grooves of interface. The theoretical basis of determination of τ was made for equal thermal conductivities of solid and liquid phases for some transparent materials. It was also determined by the help of Gunduz and Hunt numerical method¹⁵ for materials having known grain boundary shape, temperature gradient in solid and the ratio of thermal conductivity of the equilibrated liquid phases to solid phase ($R = K_L K_S$). The Gibbs-Thomson coefficient for SCN, ACT and their alloys are found in the range of $5.81-7.03 \times 10^{-8} \text{ Km}$ and is reported in Table 2.

Grain boundary is the internal surface which can be understood in a very similar way to nucleation on surfaces in liquid-solid transformation. In past, a numerical method⁴ is applied to observe the interfacial grain boundary energy (σ_{gb}) without applying the temperature gradient for the grain boundary groove shape. For isotropic interface there is no difference in the value of interfacial tension and interfacial energy. A considerable force is employed at grain boundary groove in anisotropic interface. The grain boundary energy can be obtained by the equation :

$$\sigma_{gb} = 2\sigma \cos \theta \quad (6)$$

where θ is equilibrium contact angle precipitates at solid-liquid interface of grain boundary. The grain boundary energy could be twice the solid-liquid interfacial energy in the case where the contact angle tends to zero. The value σ_{gb} for solid SCN and ACT was found to be 15.84×10^{-3} and $64.14 \times 10^{-3} \text{ J m}^{-2}$ respectively and the value for all alloys is given in Table 2.

Thermodynamic mixing functions such as, molar free

Table 3. Radius of critical nucleus (r^*) at different undercoolings (ΔT)

$\Delta T (\Delta^\circ\text{C}) \rightarrow$	2.0	2.5	3.0	3.5	4.0	4.5	5.0	5.5	6.0	6.5	7.0
Alloy ↓											
A ₁	-	3.53	-	-	3.53	-	2.83	2.57	2.36	-	2.02
A ₂	6.89	-	4.59	-	3.45	-	2.76	-	2.30	-	-
A ₃	-	-	6.71	3.83	2.25	-	2.68	2.44	-	-	-
A ₄	6.68	5.34	4.45	-	3.34	2.97	-	-	-	-	-
A ₅	-	-	4.42	-	3.31	-	2.65	-	2.21	-	1.89
A ₆	-	5.38	4.48	3.84	3.36	2.99	-	-	-	-	-
A ₇	-	4.92	4.10	3.51	2.07	2.73	-	-	-	-	-
A ₈	-	4.69	3.91	3.35	2.93	2.61	-	-	-	-	-

energy of mixing (ΔG^M), molar entropy of mixing (ΔS^M) and molar enthalpy of mixing (ΔH^M) of the binary alloys when two components are mixed (Table 4) together were determined by using the following equation^{16,17} :

$$\Delta G^M = RT_i(X_1 \ln a_1^1 + X_2 \ln a_2^1) \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta S^M = -R(X_1 \ln X_1^1 + X_2 \ln X_2^1) \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta H^M = RT_i(X_1 \ln \gamma_1^1 + X_2 \ln \gamma_2^1) \quad (9)$$

$$\mu_i^{-M} = \Delta G_i^{-M} = RT_i \ln a_i \quad (10)$$

where a is activity and, ΔG_i^{-M} is the partial molar free energy of mixing of component, i , (μ_i^{-M} chemical potential) in binary mix. The negative value of integral molar free energy of mixing of all alloys suggests that the mixing in all cases is spontaneous and there is appreciable interaction between unlike molecules. The integral molar enthalpy of mixing value corresponds to the value of excess integral molar free energy of the system favors the regularity in the binary solution. The positive value of ΔS^M for all alloys predicts the increase in randomness due to increased amplitude of phase distribution in the binary melt. The activity coefficient of components for the present system can be calculated by the equation¹⁸ :

$$-\ln X_i^1 \gamma_i^1 = \frac{\Delta H_i}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_a} - \frac{1}{T_i} \right) \quad (11)$$

where X_i^1 and γ_i^1 are the mole fraction and activity coefficient of the component 'i' in the liquid phase respectively, ΔH_i , is the heat of fusion of component 'i' at the melting point T_i and T_a is the temperature of the alloy. The values of activity coefficient of the components in alloys are given in Table 1. The decrease the value of

partial molar entropy of mixing functions with increasing mole fraction of SCN (Fig. 1) favors the interaction in the alloys.

The solid-liquid interface morphology can be predicted from the value of the entropy of fusion¹⁹. According to Hunt and Jackson²⁰, the type of growth from binary melt depends upon a factor α , defined as :

$$\alpha = \xi \frac{\Delta H}{RT} = \xi \frac{\Delta S}{R} \quad (12)$$

where ξ is a crystallographic factor depending upon the geometry of the molecules and has a value less than or equal to one. $\Delta S/R$ (also known as Jackson's roughness parameter α) is the entropy of fusion (dimensionless) and R is the gas constant. When α is less than two the solid-liquid interface is atomically rough and exhibits nonfaceted growth. The value of Jackson's roughness parameter ($\Delta S/R$) is given in Table 2. In all the alloys except A_8 under investigation the $\Delta S/R$ values are greater than two, which indicate that they exhibit faceted growth. The microstructure of SCN and ACT are shown in Fig. 2a and Fig. 2b respectively. Cellular morphology leads in A_7 (0.800 mole fraction of SCN) as a results of combined effect of large solute content and shallow temperature gradient raised due to large supercooling at solid-liquid interface. In alloy A_8 (0.370 mole fraction of SCN) the dendrite arm of SCN has been changed into interdendrite microstructure due to the rejection and multiplication of ACT molecules from supersaturated liquid. Many of side branches of dendrites have re-melted and detached from main dendrite stem and exhibits interdendritic morphology.

Table 4. Partial and integral thermodynamic mixing functions

Alloy	G_1^{-M} (J mol ⁻¹)	G_2^{-M} (J mol ⁻¹)	G^M (J mol ⁻¹)	H_1^{-M} (J mol ⁻¹)	H_2^{-M} (J mol ⁻¹)	H^M (J mol ⁻¹)	S_1^{-M} (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	S_2^{-M} (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	S^M (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
A_1	533.61	454.53	-298.41	6363.19	997.86	1081.43	15.34	1.43	3.70
A_2	474.88	760.64	-393.69	4249.66	1856.46	1499.77	10.09	2.93	5.06
A_3	432.61	959.69	-374.93	3101.05	2635.42	1717.92	7.021	4.53	5.66
A_4	381.61	1206.25	-366.81	2308.08	3497.35	1730.78	5.28	6.28	5.75
A_5	342.82	1415.45	-311.26	1739.17	4383.23	1670.02	3.87	8.22	5.49
A_6	302.69	1623.05	-242.29	1284.62	5348.78	1516.65	2.77	10.50	4.96
A_7	183.33	2221.11	-304.78	833.995	6794.73	1141.53	1.89	13.26	4.19
A_8	110.22	2574.90	-236.16	498.239	8330.01	844.24	1.15	17.03	3.20

Fig. 1. Plot of partial molar entropy of mixing quantity versus composition

Fig. 2a. Microstructure of SCN $\times 50$

Fig. 2b. Microstructure of ACT $\times 50$

Conclusion :

The emerging of solid-liquid interface is a thermodynamic phenomenon. Thus the interfacial energy is a thermodynamic quantity and the driving force of interface occurrence and interfacial energy follow the thermodynamic relationship, $\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S$. Growth kinetics of the system shows the applicability of Hillig-Turnbull equa-

tion $v = u(\Delta T)^n$. Mixing functions infer appreciable interaction among the components in alloys. The interfacial energy value and grain boundary energy value for SCN predicted in the study are in good agreement with the values obtained earlier. Microstructure of alloys supports the Jackson roughness theory of classification of materials.

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